

***IN-SITU* NEUTRON DIFFRACTION CHARACTERISATION OF A NITI-FIBRE REINFORCED SHAPE ACTIVE COMPOSITE**

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SUMMARY: This paper addresses the shape active smart composite system consisting of a NiTi continuous fibre reinforced composite based on an aluminium matrix. We have successfully manufactured a shape active composite system with quite unusual macroscopic properties. Through a thermomechanical process we induce both a forward and reverse phase transformation in the embedded fibres. We specifically focus on the utilisation of neutron diffraction for the monitoring of the on-going internal phase transformation in the composite, and successfully correlate the phase transformation with observable macroscopic measures of thermo mechanical deformation.

KEYWORDS: neutron diffraction, smart composites, shape active, continuous fibres, NiTi-reinforcement, phase transformation, internal stresses, in-situ

INTRODUCTION

Among the many candidates for smart materials or as elements of smart structures the characteristic shape memory capability of NiTi-alloys has drawn the attention of many researchers within the field of “Smart Materials and Structures”. The thermo mechanical behaviour does hold very interesting prospects for unusual and advantageous composite properties, when embedded in monolithic alloys.

Some of the first experimental investigations of this class of advanced materials [1-3] reported an increased elevated temperature flow strength in the NiTi shape memory reinforced composites relative to the unreinforced matrix alloys following a room temperature pre-strain. Armstrong and Kino [4] later subjected an experimental NiTi reinforced composite to a room temperature (RT) pre-strain process and observed unusual hardening behaviour. They subsequently exposed the composite to an unconstrained heating process and observed a spectacular non-linear thermal contraction. Similar to previously reported results they also observed a significant increase in the elevated temperature flow strength as compared to the unreinforced matrix alloy at elevated temperature as well as compared to the composite RT-behaviour.

It is well accepted that the properties of NiTi-alloys are very sensitive to the internal structure of the alloy. It has proven that the thermo mechanical process of elevated temperature consolidation of a composite material using such fibres, holds a high risk of reducing, if not eliminating, the phase transformation characteristics of the fibres. Process, temperature and time are critical and must be controlled within narrow limits.

Once produced successfully, a simple thermo mechanical test shows readily that the composite material behaves differently than a conventional metal/metal composite. However, in order to quantify that the macroscopic properties are indeed signs of an interior phase transformation in the embedded NiTi-fibres, experimental techniques other than traditional tensile testing are called for. In the present paper we particularly focus on the utilisation of neutron diffraction, whereby we selectively focus on either the embedded NiTi-fibres or on the aluminium matrix. The main aim is to demonstrate how the readily observable macroscopic effects of the phase transformation of the fibres can be directly correlated with the NiTi phase distribution by monitoring specific peak intensities and selected lattice parameters.

MATERIAL

The material under consideration is based on a 6082 aluminium alloy reinforced with continuous 50.7 at%Ni NiTi fibres of 190 μ m fibre thickness. The reinforcing fibres were laced onto 0.3mm thick end-notched sheets of the T6 heat treated matrix alloy. Sheets were stacked into a welded canister of the matrix alloy which was subsequently sealed and evacuated. The sealed can was heated to approximately 535 $^{\circ}$ C and consolidated using a maximum load of 25 metric ton. The consolidated can was water quenched, whereafter it remained at room temperature for five days before a T6 age treatment at 175 $^{\circ}$ C for 8 hours. Three test pieces of approximately 20.5vol% fibre content were subsequently machined from the can as well as a control specimen machined from an unreinforced part of the can. Fig.1 shows a micrograph of the central cross section of one of the composite specimens.

Fig. 1: Micrograph of the test specimen cross section.

NEUTRON DIFFRACTION

As mentioned we specifically focus on the utilisation of the neutron diffraction technique in the characterisation of the present materials. Using a dedicated thermo mechanical loading rig designed for in-situ diffraction experiments [5] and mounted on the TAS-8 diffractometer of the steady state DR-3 reactor at Risø, we monitor selected Bragg peak intensities and lattice parameters throughout the imposed thermo mechanical process.

Being a steady state source we are restricted to monitoring single peaks at a time, though peaks which are close together can be observed simultaneously by the installed position sensitive detector. Several peaks could be monitored by shifting the detector to a range of selected 2θ -settings though at the cost of deteriorated time resolution. In the present case we select an optimum time resolution to be the focus in the thermo mechanical processes where relaxation, creep etc. may result in a severe time dependency at specific temperatures.

We acknowledge that we get a rather limited monitoring of the complicated phase transformation process. A more complete picture would be obtained from a spallation source experiment, however, it appears unrealistic to perform an in-situ monitoring of the complete texture with the time resolution achieved in the present case where diffraction peaks are monitored at a rate ranging from one per 10 sec. to one per 90 sec.

EXPERIMENTAL

The outline of the experimental procedure is to perform an RT monitoring of the diffraction line spectre for the as-produced material in order to characterise the phase distribution of the NiTi fibres. We subsequently select a specific peak from the fibres to be our monitor of the progress in the phase transformation during the thermo mechanical process. The initial stage is an RT straining process to approximately 4% total strain, which is expected to induce an austenite-to-martensite phase transformation. Subsequently the now pre-strained test piece is subjected to an unconstrained heating process to 120°C during which the fibres are expected to recover some of the austenitic phase.

Room Temperature Characterisation

The line spectra for the as-produced test piece shown in Fig.2 clearly displays the two characteristic aluminium Bragg peaks as well as the austenite (110)-peak in-between the aluminium peaks. There is no sign of the martensitic phase in the fibre direction of the composite in the as-produced state. Following the subsequent RT straining process we repeat the diffraction line scan, and the result is superimposed on the as-produced line spectra in Fig.2. We now observe a Bragg peak at 4.6 angstrom, which was absent in the as-produced state. This peak, which is assumed to be from the martensitic phase, has been indexed in conflicting ways in a number of previous investigations [6-10] ; here it will be indexed as the martensite (001)-peak.

As the austenite (110)-peak is not well separated from the aluminium peaks, therefore we selected the martensite (001)-peak as our monitor of the progress of the phase transformation. The neutron detector was focused at this specific d-spacing range during the straining process, and the evolution of this specific Bragg peak as a function of strain is shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 2: RT diffraction line spectra for the as-produced specimen and following a 4% tensile straining process.

In Fig.3 we observe that the martensite (001)-peak intensity monotonically increases with strain; in the insert the specific strain levels at which the Bragg peaks were recorded are indicated by arrows. During the elastic part of the deformation there is no sign of the peak and then beginning at a total strain of 1.9% the peak intensity increases. A careful quantification of the peak intensity shows an increase in intensity which is approximately linear with strain and with a zero intensity intercept extrapolated to a total strain of 1%.

Fig. 3: Martensite (001)-peak intensity variation with straining.

Unconstrained Heating

The subsequent unconstrained heating process is expected to induce a recovery of some of the austenite at the cost of a reduction in content of martensite. The process is monitored by recording the macroscopic strain (or expansion) and again the neutron diffraction measurements are focused on the martensite (001)-peak. The macroscopic expansion is quite unusual as seen in Fig.4, which also displays the expected thermal expansion of the unreinforced alloy.

We note that the pre-strained composite sample displays a quite unusual non-linear thermal contraction in contrast to the normal thermal expansion of the monolithic alloy. This dramatic thermal contraction is a clear indication of the powerful shape memory response of the embedded fibres. Again these observations, based on macroscopic properties, can only qualitatively be assumed to be correlated with the internal phase transformation of the imbedded fibres, and more advanced techniques are called upon for a more direct correlation.

Fig. 4: Macroscopic expansion during unconstrained heating to 120°C for the unreinforced control specimen and for the NiTi-reinforced composite.

By using neutron diffraction we can take a step in this direction, and again we select to monitor the evolution in the martensite (001)-peak, and take the peak intensity as an indicator of the progress in the phase transformation. These results are shown in Fig.5.

From Fig.5 we clearly observe the progressive elimination of the martensite (001)-peak with temperature. In the superimposed insert of the macroscopic behaviour arrows indicate the level of thermal contraction at which the diffraction peaks were recorded. Again a careful examination shows the peak intensity to reduce essentially linearly with the macroscopic thermal contraction. The macroscopic thermal contraction can hence be directly correlated with the evolution in the phase transformation of the embedded fibres.

Fig. 5: Martensite (001)-peak intensity variation with temperature during unconstrained heating to 120°C.

As mentioned we obtain three specimens with identical process parameters from a specific can, which gives us the opportunity to repeat the test with a focus other than the martensite (001)-peak. A subsequent repetition of the entire thermo mechanical process was conducted, and for the unconstrained heating part of the process we changed the focus of the neutron diffraction experiment to the monitoring of the Al_{111} lattice expansion. This is shown in Fig.6 together with the lattice expansion of the unreinforced control specimen. Whereas the monitoring of the unreinforced lattice expansion nicely reflects the expected coefficient of thermal expansion of aluminium, the Al_{111} lattice parameter of the composite remains nearly constant until approximately 80°C, whereafter it starts to grow. The inclination is, however, smaller than for the unreinforced control specimen. The difference between the two curves is a measure of the longitudinal elastic internal strain in the aluminium matrix phase of the composite, and hence correlates the thermal contraction of the composite and the progressive reduction in the martensite content with the generation of a compressive internal strain in the matrix of the composite.

CONCLUSION

Shape active composites can be manufactured to have quite un-usual macroscopic properties which are readily monitored by traditional experimental techniques. However, in order to correlate these observations directly with the on-going phase transformation of the embedded fibres more advanced techniques are called for. We specifically focus on the utilisation of neutron diffraction, whereby we can follow the evolution of the internal phase transformation by continuously monitoring of the intensities of selected representative Bragg peaks. We have shown an essentially linear correlation between the applied strain and martensite content at room temperature.

Fig. 6: Associated Al_{111} longitudinal lattice expansion for the unreinforced control specimen and for the NiTi-reinforced composite during unconstrained heating to 120°C.

A subsequent free thermal process to 120°C showed an un-usual and dramatic thermal contraction of the composite system. By monitoring the peak intensity of a selected martensite Bragg peak we again observed an essentially linear correlation between temperature and martensite content. Furthermore, by monitoring the lattice strain evolution in the aluminium matrix phase it is observed that this reverse phase transformation and macroscopic thermal

contraction results in the development of large compressive residual strains in the matrix of the composite.

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